

1 **Bipolar seesaw control on last interglacial sea level**

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12 **Current understanding of ocean-atmosphere-cryosphere interactions at ice-age**
13 **terminations relies largely on assessments of the most recent (last) glacial-**
14 **interglacial transition¹⁻³, Termination I (T-I). But the extent to which T-I is**
15 **representative of previous terminations remains poorly constrained. Testing the**
16 **consistency of termination processes requires comparison of time series of**
17 **critical climate parameters with detailed – and hitherto elusive – absolute and**
18 **relative age control. Yet such age control has been lacking for even the**
19 **penultimate glacial termination (T-II), which culminated in a last interglacial**
20 **sea-level highstand several metres above present⁴. Here we show that Heinrich**
21 **Stadial 11 (HS11), a prominent North Atlantic cold episode^{5,6}, occurred between**
22 **135±1 to 130±2 thousand years (kyr) ago and was linked with rapid sea-level rise**
23 **during T-II. Our conclusions are based on new and existing⁶⁻⁹ data for T-II and**
24 **the last interglacial that we collate onto a single, radiometrically constrained**
25 **chronology. The HS11 cold episode^{5,6} punctuated T-II and coincided directly**
26 **with a major deglacial meltwater pulse, which predominantly entered the North**
27 **Atlantic and accounted for ~70% of the glacial-interglacial sea-level rise^{8,9}. We**
28 **conclude that, possibly in response to stronger insolation and CO₂ forcing earlier**
29 **in the termination, the relationship between climate and ice-volume changes**
30 **during T-II differed fundamentally from that of T-I, when the major sea-level**
31 **rise clearly post-dated^{3,10,11} Heinrich Stadial 1. We also find that HS11 coincided**
32 **with sustained Antarctic warming, likely through a bipolar seesaw temperature**
33 **response¹², and propose that this heat gain at high southern latitudes promoted**
34 **Antarctic ice-sheet melting that fuelled the last interglacial sea-level peak.**
35

36 Late Quaternary glacial-interglacial cycles exemplify the response of Earth's climate
37 to combined insolation and CO₂ forcing⁴. Their overall "sawtooth" structure consists
38 of gradual global cooling and ice-volume build-up during glaciations, followed by
39 rapid warming and melting during glacial terminations^{4,9,13}. Millennial-scale episodes
40 of North Atlantic cooling and ice-rafted-debris (IRD) deposition, commonly referred
41 to as Heinrich events¹⁴, punctuated each of the last five terminations^{15,16}. During T-I,
42 North Atlantic cooling and IRD events occurred during Heinrich Stadial 1 (HS1, ~18-
43 14.6 kyr ago) and the Younger Dryas (YD, ~12.8-11.5 kyr ago), which coincided with
44 weakened Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC), drought in the
45 boreal tropics, and heat build-up and strengthening of wind-driven upwelling in the
46 Southern Ocean¹. These developments were coupled with a bipolar temperature
47 "seesaw" and CO₂ release from the (Southern) ocean into the atmosphere¹. Neither
48 HS1 nor the YD appear to correspond to periods with high rates of deglacial sea level
49 rise¹¹ (so-called meltwater pulses, MWP). This raises the question of whether the
50 North Atlantic climate and sea level change were decoupled only during T-I, or if this
51 decoupling applied also to other terminations with different forcing histories.
52 Accordingly, we need detailed assessments of the relative phasing between bipolar
53 seesaw, atmospheric CO₂, and sea level through older terminations, while the absolute
54 timing of these processes allows resolving their relationship with insolation forcing.
55
56 Absolute chronologies for terminations older than T-I hinge on radiometric (U-series)
57 dating of speleothems and corals, while marine sediment cores lack such independent
58 age control. Pioneering studies placed pre-T-I terminations on radiometrically
59 constrained timescales using: (i) correlation between deep-sea benthic stable oxygen
60 isotopes ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{benthic}}$) and coral sea-level benchmarks¹⁷, (ii) inferred similarity between

61 North Atlantic sea surface temperature (SST) and an Italian speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$
62 ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{speleothem}}$) record interpreted in terms of precipitation change⁷, and (iii) inferred
63 synchronicity of North Atlantic cold events and Asian Monsoon weak episodes,
64 archived in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{speleothem}}$ time series^{16,18}. However, deep-sea hydrographic changes
65 complicate interpretation of North Atlantic $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{benthic}}$ records in terms of sea-level
66 change¹⁹, and factors other than precipitation may affect $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{speleothem}}$ in the
67 Mediterranean region⁸. Finally, the relationship between North Atlantic climate and
68 Asian Monsoon intensity may not be straightforward on millennial timescales²⁰.
69 Hence, these studies laid critical foundations, but did not deliver a conclusive,
70 quantitative (with uncertainties) chronological framework for pre-T-I terminations.
71 Among these, T-II is noteworthy because its overall insolation forcing considerably
72 exceeded that of T-I ([Extended Data Fig. 1](#)), and it culminated in an interglacial that
73 was warmer than the Holocene^{4,21}, with sea level above present⁴.
74
75 To advance the debate, we present a new radiometrically constrained chronology for
76 North Atlantic records of climate variability across T-II and the last interglacial
77 period. We use records that are co-registered in single sediment-sample series (i.e.,
78 phase relationships are unambiguous), and well-understood land-sea climate
79 relationships to transfer – with rigorous uncertainty propagation – radiometric (U-
80 series) ages to marine records. We exploit the well-documented intermediate-water
81 connectivity between the eastern and western Mediterranean Sea ([Methods](#)), and the
82 relationship between marine surface water microfossil $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and U-series-dated
83 regional $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{speleothem}}$ records^{7,8} ([Extended Data Fig. 2](#)). We generated centennially-
84 resolved $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ records for Mediterranean surface- and intermediate-water
85 dwelling planktic foraminifera *Globigerina bulloides* and *Neogloboquadrina*

86 *pachyderma* (dextral) (Methods), respectively, from western Mediterranean Ocean
87 Drilling Program (ODP) Site 975 (ODP975, Fig. 1). Next, we synchronized the
88 ODP975 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{N. pachyderma (d)}$ record to the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{N. pachyderma (d)}$ record of eastern
89 Mediterranean core LC21 (Fig. 2a; Methods). The latter was placed previously⁸ on a
90 radiometric timescale by relating its co-registered surface $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ signal to Soreq Cave
91 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{speleothem}}$. Finally, we use the co-registered $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. bulloides}$ of ODP975 to further
92 transfer the radiometric timescale to the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. bulloides}$ record of nearby ODP Sites 976
93 and 977, and core MD01-2444 and to their co-registered SST and/or IRD records of
94 North Atlantic climate variability (Extended Data Fig. 2,3, Methods).

95

96 Comparison of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. bulloides}$ from ODP975 and ODP976 on their new radiometric
97 timescale with the Corchia Cave $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{speleothem}}$ record on its own radiometric
98 chronology (Methods) reveals a striking similarity with respect to both timing and
99 magnitude of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ shifts, notably between ~140 and ~129 kyr ago (Fig. 2b). Possible
100 correlation between western Mediterranean and Corchia Cave $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ signals was
101 contemplated before⁷, but – at that stage – an alternative coupling of North Atlantic
102 warming with increased precipitation over central Italy was favoured. The two
103 interpretations lead to substantially (up to ~4 kyr) different timings for HS11. The
104 approach used here is independent of assumptions about the phasing between North
105 Atlantic climate and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{speleothem}}$. Instead, it diagnostically indicates a source-water
106 control on Corchia Cave $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{speleothem}}$; negative $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ anomalies in North Atlantic and
107 western Mediterranean surface waters – during Heinrich events¹⁴ (see below) – were
108 transmitted via the hydrological cycle to the cave catchment. The $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ similarity
109 between ODP975 and Corchia Cave provides strong and independent validation of the
110 LC21-based radiometric chronology for ODP975, and thus to the LC21-Soreq Cave

111 synchronization used previously to provide radiometric age constraints to sea-level
112 records⁸. Validation of the LC21-Soreq Cave synchronization was obtained using U-
113 series-dated Asian monsoon records⁹, so the T-II chronology of sea-level change now
114 involves agreement between three independent, radiometrically constrained
115 approaches.

116

117 Investigation of the interhemispheric climate relationships requires first an assessment
118 of consistency between our new radiometric chronology and the AICC2012 timescale
119 for the Antarctic EPICA Dome C (EDC) ice core²². Building on the notion that
120 atmospheric methane (CH₄) concentrations and Greenland/North Atlantic
121 temperatures covaried on millennial timescales²³, we compare the western
122 Mediterranean SST record (reflecting North Atlantic climate⁶) on our new
123 chronology, with the EDC CH₄ record²³ on AICC2012 (Fig. 2c). The remarkable
124 signal similarity between 131-128 kyr ago supports consistency between the two
125 independent chronologies across this interval. Such consistency plausibly extends
126 back to ~134 kyr ago, when a distinct SST maximum coincided with a CH₄ peak.
127 Although the latter is documented by a single data point in EDC, the Vostok Antarctic
128 ice core CH₄ record²⁴ appears to corroborate the occurrence of a CH₄ peak at this
129 time.

130

131 In the following we examine in millennial-scale detail the relative timing between
132 insolation, North Atlantic climate, sea level, Antarctic temperatures, and atmospheric
133 CO₂ across HS11 and the transition into the last interglacial period (Fig. 3a-f). T-II
134 contains two major meltwater pulses⁹ (MWP-2A and MWP-2B), which are centred on
135 139±1 and 133±1 kyr ago (2σ uncertainties⁸) and coincide within uncertainties with

136 two North Atlantic cooling episodes (Fig. 3c,d). MWP-2A indicates an early phase of
137 ice-sheet retreat. Similar to its T-I counterpart³ at ~19 kyr, it coincides with a short-
138 lived (~2°C) North Atlantic cooling. MWP-2B is more convincingly resolved and
139 marks a steep ~70 m sea-level rise (70% of the glacial-interglacial change) at rates of
140 28 ± 8 m kyr⁻¹ (refs. 8,9). It lagged 4 ± 1 kyr behind the boreal summer insolation rise
141 and coincided with the prominent North Atlantic cold phase, HS11 (Fig. 3b-d). Our
142 new chronology places the initiation and termination of HS11 at 135 ± 1 and 130 ± 2 kyr
143 (2σ uncertainties), respectively, and the ~0.5-kyr warm interlude⁶ that briefly
144 interrupted it at 134 ± 1 kyr (Fig. 3c), in overall agreement with the “synthetic”
145 Greenland record¹⁶ (Extended Data Figure 3). HS11 also coincided with over half of
146 the glacial-interglacial atmospheric CO₂ increase, and with ~9°C Antarctic warming¹³
147 (Fig. 3e,f). Only ~5°C of this warming can be ascribed to radiative forcing²¹, which
148 leaves ~4°C of “residual” warming that we interpret as the Southern Ocean bipolar
149 temperature seesaw response¹² to meltwater-forced AMOC collapse and attendant
150 North Atlantic cooling (Fig. 3c, d).

151

152 An intense seesaw response with strong North Atlantic cooling suggests that the
153 meltwater entered the North Atlantic. This inference is supported by major North
154 Atlantic IRD deposition (Fig. 3b), the large magnitude (>70 m) sea-level rise
155 associated with MWP-2B (maximum freshwater flux of 0.3 ± 0.04 Sv; Fig. 4a) that
156 requires intense reduction of the large northern ice-sheets, and the distinct source-
157 water-related negative shift in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of precipitation ($\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precipitation}}$) at Corchia Cave
158 (Fig. 4b), interpreted here as a reflection of meltwater-based freshening of the wider
159 North Atlantic (Methods). The seesaw response at the time of HS11 is also
160 corroborated by its agreement with the established relationship between magnitudes

161 of Antarctic warming and North Atlantic stadial duration during the last glacial cycle
162 ([Extended Data Fig. 4](#)). Finally, HS11 coincided with a weak Asian monsoon event¹⁸
163 and South American monsoon intensification²⁵, both archived in radiometrically dated
164 speleothems and interpreted in terms of a southward shift of the Intertropical
165 Convergence Zone (ITCZ) in response to AMOC weakening. The relative timing
166 between ITCZ dynamics, AMOC, and North Atlantic climate is well documented
167 across T-I and within the last glacial cycle²⁶. Similar scenarios were suggested for
168 previous terminations¹⁸ (including T-II), but required assumptions about timing
169 relationships between records. By placing all records on a single radiometrically
170 constrained chronology, our results overcome this limitation, and independently
171 corroborate the scenario for T-II.

172

173 Since ~70% of the glacial-interglacial sea-level rise (MWP-2B) occurred during a
174 phase of weak AMOC (HS11; [Fig. 3b-d](#)), T-II fundamentally differed from T-I.
175 During T-I, ~75% of the sea-level rise¹¹ post-dated the major deglacial cooling phase
176 in the North Atlantic (HS1), and the largest meltwater pulse (MWP-1A; 15-20% of
177 the deglacial sea-level rise) peaked when the North Atlantic was warm (or warming)
178 and AMOC was relatively strong (or strengthening)^{3,10,27}. This fuelled arguments that
179 Antarctic ice sheets contributed substantially to MWP-1A (ref. 10). In contrast, we
180 find that MWP-2B was more than three times larger than MWP-1A, and was tied
181 directly to circum-North Atlantic ice-sheet reduction and attendant North Atlantic
182 cooling. This fundamentally different relationship between North Atlantic climate and
183 sea level change during the last two terminations indicates that during T-II, northern
184 hemisphere ice sheets collapsed early in the termination, possibly in response to a

185 combination of overall stronger (and more rapidly rising¹⁸) boreal summer insolation
186 and higher atmospheric CO₂ ([Extended Data Figure 1](#)).

187

188 Our reconstructed phasing of interhemispheric climate developments through HS11 is
189 consistent with a southward shift and/or possible strengthening of Southern Ocean
190 westerlies²⁸, and associated subsurface oceanic warming around Antarctica²⁹. This
191 provides a mechanism for conveying the oceanic heat related to the bipolar seesaw to
192 Antarctica. The attendant excess warming of ~4°C in Antarctica²¹ (see above) during
193 HS11 would have then affected the Antarctic ice sheet stability through processes
194 such as under-ice melting and grounding line retreat of ice-shelves³⁰. To account for
195 relatively long (but poorly known) adjustment timescales of this major ice sheet to
196 warming, including the excess 4°C, we approximate heat gain/loss by integrating the
197 Antarctic temperature record over time¹³. We find that the timings of maximum heat
198 gain and the last interglacial sea-level peak⁸ match best for an overall integration
199 timescale of 0.75±0.15 kyr ([Fig. 4c](#)).

200

201 Securing records to a single, radiometrically constrained chronology reveals the
202 sequence of events through T-II. An initial (minor but significant) ice-sheet reduction
203 caused MWP-2A during a northern hemisphere insolation minimum. Next followed
204 the main phase of northern ice-sheet reduction (MWP-2B), ~4 kyr after the onset of
205 insolation rise, which caused AMOC collapse, with attendant North Atlantic cooling
206 and (see-saw) Southern Ocean warming. We infer that resultant Antarctic heating
207 drove continuation of sea-level rise well after MWP-2B, up to several metres above
208 present⁴, which predominantly reflects Antarctic ice reduction.

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322

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330 **Figure 1. Location of the palaeoclimate archives discussed in the paper and**
331 **Mediterranean circulation pattern. a**, Bathymetric map of the Mediterranean Sea
332 with locations of the marine and continental records discussed in the text. **b**, W-E
333 cross-section across the Mediterranean Sea with a sketch of the basin's anti-estuarine
334 circulation; surface inflow (blue) is through the Strait of Gibraltar and subsurface
335 (intermediate-water, red) outflow into the Atlantic Ocean ([Methods](#)). Yellow stars
336 indicate the upper intermediate water depth habitat of *Neogloboquadrina pachyderma*
337 (d) ([Methods](#)) at the location of core LC21 (35°40'N, 26°35'E, water depth 1522 m)
338 and Ocean Drilling Program (ODP) Site 975 (38°53.8'N, 4°30.6'E, water depth 2415
339 m).

340

341 **Figure 2. Construction and validation of a radiometrically constrained**
342 **chronology for western Mediterranean Sea ODP Sites 975 and 976. a**,
343 Synchronization of *Neogloboquadrina pachyderma* (d) $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ from ODP Site 975 to its
344 counterpart from eastern Mediterranean core LC21 ([Methods](#)), which was placed on a
345 radiometric chronology by ref. 8. Error bars depict the 2σ synchronization errors
346 ([Methods, Extended Data Table 1](#)). **b**, Synchronization of *Globigerina bulloides* $\delta^{18}\text{O}$
347 from ODP Site 976 (after ref. 6) to its counterpart from nearby ODP Site 975 on its
348 radiometrically constrained chronology. Error bars depict the 2σ synchronization
349 errors ([Methods, Extended Data Table 2](#)). Comparison of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. bulloides}$ from ODP
350 Sites 975 and 976 with the speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{speleothem}}$) from Corchia Cave⁷ (Italy)
351 is made to validate (not to constrain) the chronology of the western Mediterranean
352 cores. Confidence limits (95% lighter sky blue, 68% darker sky blue) for the Corchia
353 Cave $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{speleothem}}$ result from Monte Carlo analysis ([Methods](#)) of the chronological
354 and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{speleothem}}$ uncertainties (ref. 7). **c**, Comparison of the western Mediterranean

355 ODP Site 976 sea surface temperature (SST)⁶ on the radiometrically constrained
356 chronology developed in this study with the Antarctic atmospheric methane (CH₄)
357 record²³ on the AICC2012 timescale²², supporting consistency between the two
358 independent chronologies. The confidence limits for the ODP976 SST (95% light
359 grey, probability maximum with 95% uncertainty, heavier grey line and envelope)
360 and atmospheric CH₄ concentrations (95% light orange, probability maximum with
361 95% uncertainty, heavier orange line and envelope) result from Monte Carlo analysis
362 of their chronological and proxy related uncertainties, employing Gaussian filters of
363 0.2 and 0.4 kyr, respectively ([Methods](#)).

364

365 **Figure 3. Interhemispheric records of climate change across glacial Termination**

366 **II. a**, Boreal and Austral summer insolation curves³¹. **b**, Ice-rafted-debris (IRD)
367 record from core MD01-2444, Iberian Margin¹⁹ (North Atlantic). **c**, Sea surface
368 temperature (SST) record from ODP Site 976, western Mediterranean Sea⁶. The 95%
369 confidence intervals (light grey envelope) and probability maximum (heavier grey
370 line) and its associated 95% confidence intervals (heavier grey envelope) of the SST
371 record are based on a Monte Carlo analysis of chronological and SST uncertainties,
372 employing a 0.2 kyr Gaussian filter ([Methods](#)). Profiles in **b** and **c** are on the
373 radiometrically constrained chronology developed in this study ([Methods](#)). **d**, Rates of
374 relative sea level change with associated 95% confidence limits (magenta shaded
375 envelopes) of the probability maximum (magenta solid line) from Monte Carlo
376 analysis of uncertainties in the relative sea-level reconstructions and chronology⁹. **e**,
377 Composite atmospheric CO₂ concentrations from EPICA Dome C (EDC) ([Methods](#)).
378 **f**, Antarctic air temperatures¹³ (ΔT) from EDC. The 95% confidence intervals (light
379 blue envelope) and probability maximum (heavier blue line) and its associated 95%
380 confidence intervals (heavier blue envelope) of the ΔT record are based on a Monte

381 Carlo analysis of chronological and ΔT uncertainties, employing a 0.2 kyr Gaussian
382 filter ([Methods](#)). HS11, Heinrich Stadial 11; MWP, meltwater pulse.

383

384 **Figure 4. Origin and impacts of meltwater pulses during glacial termination II.**

385 **a**, Freshwater fluxes calculated ([Supplementary Information](#)) from rates of sea-level
386 change⁹. **b**, Ice-volume and temperature corrected $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of Corchia Cave speleothem
387 ([Methods](#)), indicating isotopic anomalies of precipitation in the cave catchment.

388 Envelopes are the 95% confidence limits of the probability maximum (solid line)

389 obtained from a Monte Carlo approach that takes into account proxy related and

390 chronological uncertainties of the various records ([Methods](#)). **c**, Relative Sea Level

391 (RSL)⁹. The 95% confidence limits (light magenta) and the probability maximum

392 with 95% uncertainty (heavy magenta line and shading) were presented in ref. 9. **d**,

393 Antarctic heat loss/gain obtained by integrating the Antarctic temperatures¹³ over a

394 period of 0.75 ± 0.15 kyr, using a Monte Carlo approach employing a 0.8 kyr Gaussian

395 filter of the data (blue).

396

397

398

399 **METHODS**

400 **Core material.** Ocean Drilling Program (ODP) Site 975 was drilled by R/V *Joides*
401 *Resolution* in the western Mediterranean Sea (Fig. 1; 38°53.8'N, 4°30.6'E; water
402 depth 2,416 m). ODP Site 975 is located on the Menorca Rise³², along the path of the
403 Atlantic surface water entering the Mediterranean Sea through the Strait of Gibraltar
404 and flowing eastward across the basin³³⁻³⁶. Sections 2H4 to 2H6 from ODP Site 975
405 Hole C were sampled using u-channels, and subsequently sliced at 1 cm resolution.
406 Data were generated for this study at a resolution of 1 to 2 cm.

407

408

409 **Stable oxygen ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$) and carbon ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) isotopes.** For ODP Site 975, 20-30
410 individuals of *Globigerina bulloides* (300-355 μm size fraction) and 10-20 individuals
411 of *Neogloboquadrina pachyderma* (d) (212-250 μm size fraction) were picked. For
412 core LC21, 10-15 individuals of *N. pachyderma* (d) (250-300 μm size fraction) were
413 picked to increase the resolution and spliced together with previously published
414 records^{8,37} between 143 and 129 kyr ago. To avoid complications arising from size-
415 dependent vital effects in planktic foraminifera^{38,39}, we constrained the size window
416 of the picked foraminifera from ODP Site 975 and core LC21 to a maximum of ~55
417 μm . This compromised the continuity of the *G. bulloides* $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ records
418 between 129 and 127 kyr ago in ODP Site 975, as *G. bulloides* abundance drops
419 significantly in that interval, and insufficient numbers were available in one strict size
420 window.

421

422 Prior to analysis, foraminiferal samples were crushed, cleaned and ultrasonicated
423 briefly in methanol. The cleaned samples were then analysed ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$) at the
424 Australian National University with a Thermo Finnigan Delta Advantage mass
425 spectrometer coupled to a Kiel IV carbonate device, in which samples react with
426 105% phosphoric acid at 75°C. Results were normalized to the Vienna Peedee
427 Belemnite (VPDB) scale with the NBS-19 ($\delta^{18}\text{O} = -2.20\text{‰}$, $\delta^{13}\text{C} = 1.95\text{‰}$) and NBS-
428 18 ($\delta^{18}\text{O} = -23.20\text{‰}$, $\delta^{13}\text{C} = -5.014\text{‰}$) carbonate standards. External reproducibility
429 (1σ) of a carbonate standard (NBS-19) was better than $\pm 0.08\text{‰}$ for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\pm 0.06\text{‰}$
430 for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.

431

432

433 **Construction and validation of a radiometrically constrained chronology for**
434 **ODP Site 975.** Synchronization of western Mediterranean ODP Site 975 to eastern
435 Mediterranean core LC21 exploits the strong oceanographic connectivity between the
436 two Mediterranean sub-basins at intermediate depths. Vigorous intermediate
437 circulation transports water westward from the Rhodes Gyre (nearby core LC21, [Fig.](#)
438 [1](#)), to the western Mediterranean, and eventually through the Strait of Gibraltar as
439 Mediterranean outflow into the Atlantic Ocean (e.g., refs. 33-36). Data⁴⁰ and
440 numerical modelling⁴¹ indicate that this intermediate-water connection is an enduring
441 feature of Mediterranean circulation through time. Accordingly, characterization of
442 past geochemical property changes in intermediate waters across the Mediterranean
443 provides a valuable tool for synchronizing sediment cores from different sectors of
444 the basin. To characterize variability of the intermediate waters at ODP Site 975 and
445 core LC21, we use new (see above) and existing^{8,37} $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ data for the upper
446 intermediate-water dwelling³⁸ planktic foraminifer *N. pachyderma* (d).

447

448 Based on the enduring intermediate-water connection, the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{N. pachyderma (d)}$ profile of
449 ODP Site 975 is synchronized with that of LC21 (Fig. 2a, Extended Data Fig. 5), for
450 which a radiometrically constrained chronology was recently developed, based on a
451 strong surface-water $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ relationship with $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in speleothems ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{speleothem}}$) in
452 Soreq Cave (Israel)⁸. Specifically, we identified ten $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{N. pachyderma (d)}$ shifts, each
453 represented by multiple (ranging from 3 to 34) data-points, and used their mid-points
454 to place the ODP Site 975 records onto the LC21 chronology of ref. 8 (Fig. 2a,
455 Extended Data Fig. 5a). We linearly interpolated ages between age control points,
456 assuming constant sedimentation rates between them. We adopted this approach
457 because there is no evidence to suggest highly variable sedimentation rates at ODP
458 Site 975. In addition, this assumption does not affect the age of the individual tie-
459 points and hence our conclusions, given that the timing of HS11 is constrained by
460 four age control points.

461

462 The ODP Site 975 and LC21 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{N. pachyderma (d)}$ profiles are virtually identical between
463 ~143 and ~132 kyr ago. An abrupt shift to lighter values at ~132 kyr ago follows at
464 ODP Site 975, while it is not observed in LC21. Next, the ODP Site 975 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{N.}$
465 *pachyderma (d)* stabilizes at values of ~1.6‰ before shifting again at 129 kyr (as does its
466 LC21 counterpart) to reach a distinct minimum 128 kyr ago. The interval between
467 132 and 130 kyr ago coincides with the strongest phase of Heinrich Stadial 11
468 (HS11), when, according to our analysis, the meltwater discharge into the North
469 Atlantic Ocean reached its maximum (see main text). This delivered large volumes of
470 isotopically light freshwater to the North Atlantic and (via the Strait of Gibraltar) to
471 the western Mediterranean Sea. Similar to (smaller) events during the last glacial

472 cycle⁴², such influxes would have affected intermediate levels of the water column,
473 e.g., through winter mixing in the northwestern Mediterranean⁴³, where ODP Site 975
474 is located (Fig. 1). Between 128 and 121 kyr ago, the ODP Site 975 and LC21 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{N}$.
475 *pachyderma* (d) records diverge somewhat (although both become more positive at 126-
476 123 kyr ago). This is likely due to enhanced stratification in the eastern Mediterranean
477 during the monsoon-related freshwater inputs along the North African Margin^{36-38,44-}
478 ⁴⁶. From ~121 to ~117 kyr ago, there is a similar magnitude positive shift in the ODP
479 Site 975 and LC21 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{N}$. *pachyderma* (d) records.

480

481 Our inferred synchronization of marine sediment records and the accuracy of the
482 radiometrically constrained chronology we derived for ODP Site 975 can be
483 independently validated. First, we did not use the $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{N}$. *pachyderma* (d) profiles for
484 ODP975 and core LC21 to constrain the synchronization between the two sites but
485 use those data on the synchronized age model for validation purposes (Extended Data
486 Fig. 5b). There is a remarkable agreement between the ODP975 and LC21 $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{N}$.
487 *pachyderma* (d) profiles particularly between 129 and 126 kyr ago and between 123 and
488 120 kyr ago, when both records have considerably lighter values than in the preceding
489 glacial and deglacial periods (Extended Data Fig. 5b). The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{N}$. *pachyderma* (d)
490 minimum is a characteristic feature of intervals of sapropel deposition in the eastern
491 Mediterranean and testifies to subsurface accumulation of isotopically light
492 respiration products in response to decreased deep sea ventilation^{36-38,45,47}. With an
493 isotopic shift in excess of -3‰, this feature is particularly prominent during last
494 interglacial sapropel S5 (ref. 38), which is well-documented^{37,46,48,49} and precisely
495 dated⁸ (~128 to ~121 kyr ago) in core LC21. Contemporaneous $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{N}$. *pachyderma* (d)
496 minima in both core LC21 and ODP Site 975 during S5, therefore, supports our

497 synchronization, in that they indicate that a low- $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ anomaly has been effectively
498 transferred via intermediate waters from the eastern to the western Mediterranean
499 basin, in line with previous studies⁴⁰. The ~ 2 kyr shift to heavier $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{N. pachyderma}$ (d)
500 values between 126 and 124 kyr ago at ODP Site 975 reflects an interval of
501 potentially weakened sapropel conditions in the eastern Mediterranean during which
502 deep-sea ventilation may have intermittently resumed^{37,44,45} and the transport of low-
503 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ water to the western basin interrupted. Second, between 140 and 129 kyr ago
504 there is a strong similarity between changes in the ODP Site 975 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. bulloides}$ and
505 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{speleothem}}$ from Corchia Cave (Fig. 2b). This indicates that the large negative shift
506 in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{speleothem}}$ between ~ 135 and ~ 130 kyr ago resulted mostly from a ^{18}O -
507 depletion of similar magnitude in the source of precipitation for Corchia, which at
508 present⁵⁰ and on glacial-interglacial timescales⁵¹ is the wider North Atlantic
509 Ocean/western Mediterranean Sea. Note that source water influence on $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{speleothem}}$ is
510 a common feature of the Mediterranean cave records^{8,36,52,53}. This interpretation is
511 further corroborated by the fact that increase in speleothem growth rates and decrease
512 in speleothem $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ did not occur before ~ 130 kyr ago⁷ and by a similarly timed
513 growth rate increase in a nearby cave⁵⁴. Concurrence of these climate signals in the
514 mid-latitude speleothems indicates a transition from drier/colder to wetter/warmer
515 conditions⁷ that therefore occurred at the end of the large negative $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{speleothem}}$ shift,
516 i.e., after 130 kyr ago.

517

518

519 **Transferring the ODP Site 975 chronology to ODP Sites 976 and 977 and to core**
520 **MD01-2444.** The $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. bulloides}$ record for core ODP Site 975 is used to transfer our
521 new radiometrically constrained chronology of ODP Site 975 to $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. bulloides}$ in other

522 western Mediterranean (ODP Sites 976 and 977) and Iberian Margin (North Atlantic,
523 MD01-2444) sediment cores (Fig. 2b, Extended Data Fig. 3a,c). Alignment of co-
524 registered (same sample series) alkenone-based sea surface temperature (SST) records
525 from ODP Site 977 and core MD01-2444 with that from ODP Site 976 lends credence
526 to the robustness of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. \textit{bulloides}}$ -based synchronization (Extended Data Fig.
527 5b,d).

528

529 **Propagation of chronological uncertainties.** Propagation of chronological
530 uncertainties through the various synchronization steps used in this study to transfer
531 the chronology of core LC21 (ref. 8) to ODP Site 975 and then to ODP Site 976, ODP
532 Site 977, and core MD01-2444 follows the exact same approach used by Grant et al.
533 (ref. 8). The steps are outlined below.

- 534 i) From core LC21 to ODP Site 975. For LC21 the chronological uncertainty at
535 each depth level was obtained by linearly interpolating the uncertainties
536 between the tie-points used for transferring the radiometric chronology of Soreq
537 Cave to LC21 (ref. 8). Next we calculate root-mean-square errors (MSE) that
538 propagate all the chronological uncertainties involved in the synchronization of
539 ODP Site 975 to LC21. Specifically, we include the dating error associated with
540 the LC21 chronology of Grant et al. (ref. 8), the sample spacing of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{N. \textit{pachyderma}}$
541 *pachyderma* (d) record in core LC21, the sample spacing of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{N. \textit{pachyderma}}$ (d) in ODP
542 Site 975, and extra uncertainty (2 or 3 times the sample spacing) for more
543 ambiguous tie-points (indicated in red in the Extended Data Table 1).
- 544 ii) From ODP Site 975 to ODP Site 976. For ODP Site 975, the chronological
545 uncertainty at each depth level was obtained by linearly interpolating the
546 uncertainties between the tie-points used for transferring the radiometrically

547 constrained chronology of LC21 to ODP Site 975. Next we use root-mean-
548 square errors (MSE) that propagate all the chronological uncertainties involved
549 in the synchronization of ODP Site 975 to ODP Site 976. This includes the ODP
550 Site 975 chronological uncertainty from (i), the sample spacing of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. \textit{bulloides}}$
551 in ODP Site 975, the sample spacing of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. \textit{bulloides}}$ in ODP Site 976, and extra
552 uncertainty (2 or 3 times the sample spacing) for more ambiguous tie-points
553 ([Extended Data Table 2](#)).

554 iii) From ODP Site 975 to ODP Sites 977: we include the ODP Site 975
555 chronological uncertainty (as reported in ii), the sample spacing of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. \textit{bulloides}}$
556 in ODP Site 975, the sample spacing of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. \textit{bulloides}}$ in ODP Site 977, and extra
557 uncertainty (2 or 3 times the sample spacing) for more ambiguous tie-points.
558 These uncertainties were propagated as root-mean-square errors (MSE)
559 ([Extended Data Table 3](#)).

560 iv) From ODP Site 975 to core MD01-2444: we include the ODP Site 975
561 chronological uncertainty from (as reported in ii), the sample spacing of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. \textit{bulloides}}$
562 *bulloides* in ODP Site 975, the sample spacing of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. \textit{bulloides}}$ in core MD01-
563 2444, and extra uncertainty (2 or 3 times the sample spacing) for more
564 ambiguous tie-points. These uncertainties were propagated as root-mean-square
565 errors (MSE) ([Extended Data Table 4](#)).

566

567 **EPICA Dome C (EDC) records of atmospheric CO₂ and CH₄ concentrations and**
568 **Antarctic temperatures on AICC2012.** Existing records of atmospheric CO₂ and
569 CH₄ concentrations and Antarctic atmospheric temperatures were placed on the latest
570 ice-core chronology (AICC2012)^{22,55}. For atmospheric CO₂ concentrations ([Fig. 3e](#)), a

571 composite was made of the records by Landais et al. (ref. 56) and Schneider et al. (ref.
572 57).

573

574 **Probabilistic assessment of the time series.** We performed a probabilistic
575 assessment of uncertainties for several of the new and previously published proxy
576 records discussed in our study (e.g., [Fig. 2b,c](#), [3c,f](#)) in order to evaluate their
577 confidence levels, taking into full account the uncertainties associated with both their
578 chronologies (X) and proxy measurements/calibrations (Y). This analysis of the time
579 series relies on Monte Carlo-style simulations of the input data using MATLAB. For
580 each time series, all individual data points are separately and randomly sampled
581 10,000 times within their X- and Y-uncertainties. The “Y-uncertainties”, related to the
582 proxy reconstructions (e.g., sea surface temperature) are taken from the original
583 source (e.g., Martrat et al., refs. 6,58,59). The “X-uncertainties”, related to the
584 chronologies of the various records are either taken from the error propagation
585 discussed above (Mediterranean and North Atlantic records) or from the original
586 source (Corchia Cave⁷, sea level^{8,9} and Antarctic ice core records^{22,55}). Each of the
587 10,000 iterations was then either linearly interpolated (e.g., [Fig. 2b](#)) or smoothed
588 using a Gaussian filter of defined time window (e.g., [Fig. 2c](#)). Next, the probability
589 distribution of the 10,000 iterations was assessed per time step, which allowed
590 determination of the 68% (16th-84th percentile) and 95% (2.5th-97.5th percentile)
591 probability intervals for the data. Finally, we determined the probability maximum
592 (modal value) at each time step, and its uncertainties (notably, the 95% probability
593 interval for the probability maximum). For details on this approach, see refs. 8,60.

594

595

596 **Relationships between sea level and seawater oxygen isotopes.** The response of
597 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in planktic foraminifera from the eastern Mediterranean Sea to sea-level change
598 has recently been quantified⁶⁰. This builds on the notion that sea level controls water
599 exchange between the Mediterranean Sea and the Atlantic Ocean through the Strait of
600 Gibraltar and, in turn, the residence time of waters in the basin⁶⁰⁻⁶². Because of the
601 highly evaporative conditions over the Mediterranean region, a longer residence time
602 of water leads to higher salinity and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of seawater, which is, in turn, archived in
603 the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of foraminiferal calcite^{38,60,62}. Here we use results from the model of ref. 60
604 to decipher the “glacial ^{18}O -enrichment” in eastern Mediterranean seawater, which is
605 approximated by a second-order polynomial regression ([Extended Data Fig. 6](#)). Note
606 that the generous uncertainties associated with the regression are mostly systematic⁶⁰
607 and therefore have minor impacts on the relative seawater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{seawater}}$) shifts
608 assessed here. Next, we (re)calculate the relationship between sea-level lowering and
609 mean open-ocean $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{seawater}}$ due to freshwater loss from the ocean to the continental
610 ice sheets during glacial times. This was done before⁶³, but here we use the latest sea-
611 level assessment for the last glacial maximum¹¹ (LGM) and the contemporaneous
612 oceanic $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{seawater}}$ value reconstructed from pore water analyses of deep-sea cores⁶³.
613 Finally, we evaluate the response of western Mediterranean $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{seawater}}$ to sea-level
614 change by employing a linear mixing model of the open ocean ($30\pm 5\%$) and eastern
615 Mediterranean ($70\pm 5\%$) end-members at each sea-level value that probabilistically
616 evaluates the uncertainties in the various regressions. This mixing ratio is consistent
617 with the range of salinity gradients across the Mediterranean Sea under present-day
618 and LGM boundary conditions⁶⁴.
619
620

621 **Corchia Cave palaeoprecipitation $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ changes and source water effect during**
622 **Termination II (T-II).** To obtain a time series of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ anomaly of precipitation
623 ($\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precipitation}}$) in the catchment area of Corchia Cave between 145 and 115 ka
624 (shown in Fig. 4b) we “deconstructed” the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{speleothem}}$ into its main components.
625 These include the cave temperature that controls the isotopic fractionation between
626 dripping water and inorganic (speleothem) calcite^{65,66} and the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of precipitation
627 ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precipitation}}$). The latter reflects the interplay of two independent factors: (i) the
628 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of the mean marine source of precipitation, for which variability depends on the
629 glacial ^{18}O -enrichment (see above), and (ii) the residual, here referred to as
630 $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precipitation}}$ component, which reflects variations in the isotopic composition of
631 precipitation either due to inputs of isotopically light freshwater to the North Atlantic
632 and (via Gibraltar) to the western Mediterranean Sea (e.g., from melting ice sheets) or
633 due to changes in the amount of precipitation⁶⁷.

634

635 Our approach relies on the assumption that the temperature change within the cave
636 reflects to mean annual temperature changes in the regional climate⁷, as reflected in
637 the western Mediterranean SST. We also consider the propagated chronological
638 uncertainties of the three records used to derive the $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precipitation}}$ time series. To
639 probabilistically evaluate the impacts of these assumptions and uncertainties on
640 $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precipitation}}$, we have used a Monte Carlo approach (see above), in which the SST
641 record⁶, the sea-level driven mean ocean $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{seawater}}$, and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{speleothem}}$ from Corchia
642 Cave are given as input data along with the propagated chronological uncertainties.
643 Note that calculation of the $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precipitation}}$ using a glacial mean ocean ^{18}O -enrichment
644 and a western Mediterranean ^{18}O -enrichment are statistically indistinguishable across
645 the interval of interest. This analysis is possible here for the first time because we

646 placed all relevant records on the same timescale with rigorous assessment of the
647 propagated uncertainties.
648
649 The negative $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precipitation}}$ shift in Corchia Cave during HS11 had a magnitude of
650 $\sim 1.5\text{‰}$ (Fig. 4b). An order of magnitude mass-balance assessment suggests that a ^{18}O -
651 depletion by 1.5‰ in the wider North Atlantic and western Mediterranean source
652 areas for precipitation to Corchia Cave⁶⁸ is consistent with addition of ~ 0.3 Sverdrup
653 (Sv, $10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$; Fig. 4a) of isotopically light (assumed -40‰) melt-water to a 80 m
654 deep mixed layer with $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of 1‰ (ref. 69). This implies a mixing ratio between
655 marine and meltwater end-members of 40:1 and scales the marine flux in the
656 Subtropical Atlantic to approximately 12 Sv. Despite the roughness of our calculation
657 this overall agrees with a complete collapse of the thermohaline component of the Gulf
658 Stream in the Subtropical North Atlantic during HS11 and with the persistence of
659 only the wind-driven marine transport, which today accounts for ~ 17 Sv (ref. 70).
660

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815

816
817 **Extended Data Figure 1. Orbital parameters, insolation forcing, and**
818 **atmospheric CO₂ concentrations during the last two glacial-interglacial**
819 **transitions. a and f**, Incoming solar radiation on June 21st and December 21st at 65°N
820 (orange) and 65°S (blue), respectively³¹. **b and g**, Precession of the Earth's axis³¹. **d**
821 **and i**, Eccentricity of the Earth's orbit³¹. Note the different axis scales in **c** and **h**. **d**
822 **and i**, Obliquity of the Earth's axis³¹. Different orbital configurations during glacial
823 terminations I (T-I) and II (T-II) led to markedly different insolation forcing^{31,71-73},
824 with the summer 65°N insolation increase during T-II exceeding by ~35% (~23 W m⁻²)
825 and occurring at faster rates¹⁸ than during T-I. **e and g**, atmospheric CO₂
826 concentrations during T-I (refs. 74-76) and T-II (⁵⁶). Yellow bands illustrate the
827 timing of Heinrich stadial 1 (HS1) and 11 (H11), following previous literature¹ and
828 this study, respectively. Dashed blue lines highlight that atmospheric CO₂
829 concentrations were systematically higher during T-I than during T-II. Symbols
830 indicate the maxima and/or minima in insolation, precession, eccentricity, and
831 obliquity cycles.

832
833 **Extended Data Figure 2. Flowchart of the approach used to construct and**
834 **validate chronologies of the various records.**

835
836 **Extended Data Figure 3. Synchronization of western Mediterranean Sea Ocean**
837 **Drilling Program (ODP) Site 975 to ODP Site 977 and Iberian Margin core**
838 **MD01-2444. a**, Synchronization of *Globigerina bulloides* δ¹⁸O from western
839 Mediterranean ODP Site 977 to its counterpart from nearby ODP Site 975. Error bars
840 depict 2σ synchronization errors ([Methods](#), [Extended Data Table 3](#)). The *Globigerina*
841 *bulloides* δ¹⁸O from ODP Site 976 is only shown for comparison and is not used to

842 transfer our new, radiometrically constrained chronology, to ODP Site 977 ([Methods](#)).

843 **b**, Validation of the synchronization exercise shown in **a** by comparing the alkenone-
844 based sea surface temperature (SST) records from ODP Sites 977 and 976, on their
845 new, radiometrically constrained chronology. The 95% confidence intervals (light
846 grey envelope) and probability maximum (heavier grey line) and its associated 95%
847 confidence intervals (heavier grey envelope) of the ODP Site 976 SST record are
848 based on a Monte Carlo analysis of chronological and SST uncertainties, employing a
849 0.2 kyr Gaussian filter ([Methods](#)). The synthetic record of Greenland climate
850 variability¹⁶ is also shown. **c**, Synchronization of the *Globigerina bulloides* $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ from
851 Iberian Margin (Atlantic Ocean) core MD01-2444 to its counterpart from ODP Site
852 975 (Western Mediterranean, [Methods](#)). Error bars depict 2σ synchronization errors
853 ([Methods, Extended Data Table 3](#)). The *Globigerina bulloides* $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ from ODP Site
854 976 is shown for comparison and is not used to transfer the MD01-2444 records to
855 our new, radiometrically constrained chronology ([Methods](#)). **d**, Validation of the
856 synchronization exercise shown in **c** by comparing alkenone-based SST records from
857 core MD01-2444 and ODP Site 976 (shaded enveloped as in **b**), on their new
858 radiometrically constrained chronology. The synthetic record of Greenland climate
859 variability¹⁶ is also shown.

860

861 **Extended Data Figure 4. Relationship between the duration of the North Atlantic**
862 **cold phases (stadials) and the magnitude of Antarctic warming. a**, Greenland
863 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{ice}}$ time series⁷⁷ (light blue). The probability maximum (solid blue line) and
864 associated 95% confidence bounds (shaded blue envelope) of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{ice}}$ record result
865 from 10,000 Monte Carlo simulations, employing a 0.15 kyr Gaussian filter through
866 the data and their chronological and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{ice}}$ uncertainties (see [Methods](#)). **b**, EPICA

867 Dome C (EDC) temperature reconstructions (ΔT) based on δD_{ice} data¹³ (light red).
868 The probability maximum (solid red line) and associated 95% confidence bounds
869 (shaded red envelope) of the temperature record result from 10,000 Monte Carlo
870 simulations, employing a 0.2 kyr Gaussian filter through the data and their
871 chronological and ΔT uncertainties. **c**, Comparison between Antarctic temperature
872 reconstructions from EDC using the methods of Jouzel et al. (ΔT , ref. 13) and Stenni
873 et al. (T_{SITE} , ref. 78), revealing no difference in the amplitude of the estimated
874 Antarctic temperature shifts. **d**, relationship between duration of Greenland stadials
875 and Antarctic warming for bipolar seesaw events highlighted in **a** and **b** by yellow
876 bands. Greenland and Antarctic records are on the latest ice core chronology
877 AICC2012 (ref. 55). Error bars depict 1σ uncertainty in the magnitude and duration of
878 North Atlantic cooling.

879

880 **Extended Data Figure 5. Synchronization of western Mediterranean Sea Ocean**
881 **Drilling Program (ODP) Site 975 to eastern Mediterranean core LC21. a**,
882 Synchronization of the *Neogloboquadrina pachyderma* (d) $\delta^{18}O$ from ODP Site 975
883 to its counterpart from eastern Mediterranean core LC21 ([Methods](#)), which was
884 placed on a radiometric chronology by ref. 8. Error bars depict the 2σ synchronization
885 errors ([Methods](#)). **b**, Validation of the synchronization exercise shown in **a** by
886 comparing the respective co-registered *Neogloboquadrina pachyderma* (d) $\delta^{13}C$
887 profiles from the same cores.

888

889 **Extended Data Figure 6. Glacial ^{18}O -enrichment in oceanic and Mediterranean**
890 **seawater.** Blue (open ocean), black (eastern Mediterranean Sea), and green (western
891 Mediterranean Sea) lines illustrate the relationship between seawater $\delta^{18}O$

892 ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{seawater}}$) and relative sea level (RSL). The open ocean relationship has be re-
893 calculated here using the latest assessment (grey symbol) of the sea-level lowstand
894 (Lambeck et al., 2014) of the Last Glacial Maximum (26.5-19 ka, ref. 79) and the
895 mean ocean $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{seawater}}$ value derived from pore water analyses in a suite of deep-sea
896 cores⁶³. The eastern Mediterranean relationship is derived from the model presented
897 in ref. 60. The western Mediterranean relationship (green line) reflects linear mixing
898 between eastern Mediterranean (black line) and open ocean (blue line) end-members,
899 assuming that the residence time effect^{60,62} on $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{seawater}}$ (and salinity) in the western
900 Mediterranean is $70\pm 5\%$ of that in eastern Mediterranean⁶⁴. Shaded envelopes are 1σ
901 confidence bounds, derived from probabilistic analysis of uncertainties.

902

903 **Extended Data Table 1. Summary of the uncertainties (1σ) associated with the**
904 **tie-points used for the synchronization of Ocean Drilling Program Site 975**
905 **(ODP975) to LC21.** Sample spacing uncertainties in ODP975 and LC21 and dating
906 uncertainties of LC21 (ref. 7) are combined in mean squared estimates (MSE). Tie-
907 points in red include extra uncertainty (3 times the sample spacing).

908

909 **Extended Data Table 2. Summary of the uncertainties (1σ) associated with the**
910 **tie-points used for the synchronization of Ocean Drilling Program Site 976**
911 **(ODP976) to 975 (ODP975).** Sample spacing uncertainties in ODP976 and ODP975
912 and dating uncertainties of ODP975 (see Extended Table 1) are combined in mean
913 squared estimates (MSE). Tie-points in red include extra uncertainty (3 times the
914 sample spacing).

915

916 **Extended Data Table 3. Summary of the uncertainties (1σ) associated with the**
917 **tie-points used for the synchronization of Ocean Drilling Program Site 977**
918 **(ODP977) to 975 (ODP975).** Sample spacing uncertainties in ODP977 and ODP975
919 and dating uncertainties of ODP975 (see Extended Table 1) are combined in mean
920 squared estimates (MSE).

921

922 **Extended Data Table 4. Summary of the uncertainties (1σ) associated with the**
923 **tie-points used for the synchronization of core MD01-2444 to Ocean Drilling**
924 **Program Site 975 (ODP975).** Sample spacing uncertainties in MD01-2444 and
925 ODP975 and dating uncertainties of ODP975 (see Extended Table 1) are combined in
926 mean squared estimates (MSE).

927

